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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Face Serum Using *Clitoria Ternatea*

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ABSTRACT

These days, the demand for skin care products and treatments has increased to a larger extent. Having a proper appearance and a beauty standard has gotten a lot of importance. A typical skin care routine consists of a cleanser, a serum, a moisturizer and a sunscreen. Serum has a quick absorption and ability to penetrate deep layers of the skin, as well as a non-oily finish and a deep formula with a very high amount of active ingredients. Cosmetic Serum is a highly concentrated product based on water or oil. Among these, it has been seen that the serums are the new go to when it comes to building an excellent skin routine. Serums come in various types of formulation be it for oily, dry or anything in between type of skin. The herbal facial serum was evaluated for various parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, viscosity, spreadability, antimicrobial assay and homogeneity. The results showed that all the formulations produced satisfactory results and the use of herbs in the serum will produce a successful alternative to other harmful chemical cosmetics.

INTRODUCTION

The word cosmetics was derived from the Greek word “kosmtikos” meaning having the power, arrange, skill in Decorating. Cosmetics, means any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on or introduced into or otherwise applied to human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering

appearance and includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetic. ‘Cosmeceuticals’ can be referred to as topical cosmetic pharmaceutical hybrids intended to enhance beauty through ingredients that provide additional health related functions or benefits.[1] Ayurvedic cosmeceuticals are particularly trusted for their safe, comprehensive effects and use of natural herbal extracts. Drawing from the extensive

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knowledge of Ayurveda, maintaining beauty and skin health involves balancing the three doshas (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha) and the body tissues (Rasa, Rakta, and Mamas). [2] Consequently, there is a growing emphasis on skin health, with people turning to various products such as creams, lotions, and serums to mitigate these effects and slow down the aging process. A quality skin serum has the potential to enhance skin firmness, smoothness, minimize pores, and boost moisture levels.[3]

SKIN

All skin types need these ingredients to be as healthy as possible. Gel and liquids preparations are best for oily and combination skin, serums and light lotions are best for normal to dry skin, more emollient lotions and moisturizing creams are best for dry to very dry skin. Texture is all about skin type-but the brilliant ingredients for healthy skin the same for everyone, regardless of product, texture or personal preference. Skin is a protective And largest organ of body which is struggles to heal and repair itself 24 hrs. but sometimes skin can develop dry patches for many reasons like UV rays, pollutants, makeup left on overnight can cause irritation or allergic reactions. The facial serum includes several ingredients associated with improvement in the appearance of fine Lines and wrinkles and increased barrier function including a neuro peptide. The skin is the body's outermost and Most superficial layer, It approximately 15-20% of the body's total mass. The skin is a constantly changing organ made up of numerous specialised cells and structures. As we become older, changes in the skin's form have an Impact on how it looks.

SKIN LAYERS:

- **Epidermis:**

The outermost layer of the skin that provides a barrier against environmental damage. Contains melanin, which determines skin color produces new skin cells helps maintain the body's moisture Has five layers: stratum basale, stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum, stratum lucidum and stratum corneum

- **Dermis:**

Lies below the epidermis, containing collagen and elastin fibers, responsible for skin's elasticity and strength. This layer also contains hair follicles, sweat glands, and blood vessels.

- **Hypodermis (Subcutaneous Fat):**

The bottom layer of skin that stores energy, insulates the body, and connects skin to muscles and bones. Made up of mostly fat cells and connective tissue.

SERUM

Serum is a highly concentrated cosmetic product frequently utilized in the field of cosmetology, with its origins rooted in professional skincare. Serums are cosmetic products that penetrate deep into the skin layers and release active ingredients.[4] Serum is defined as light, easily absorbed oil or water based liquids that spread on the skin. It gets rapidly absorbed and easily penetrate into the deeper layers of the skin .Also has non-greasy finish and intensive formula which Contain high concentration of active substances. Face serum delivers the active ingredient into the skin and removes the use of hazardous chemicals in giving instant results. A high-quality face serum moisturizes, soothes and reduces the size of skin pores and increases moisture. All products have anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant properties and the ingredients used in the serum should have these properties, suitable for all skin types. Gels and liquid preparations were best for

oily and combination skin, serums and lotions for normal and dry skin, and emollient creams and moisturizing creams For dry and very dry skin.[5] This high concentration allows serums to address cosmetic concerns more rapidly and effectively than traditional creams. A serum is characterized by its rapid absorption, deep penetration into the skin's layers, non-greasy texture, and highly concentrated formula containing active substances. It typically comes in the form of a gel, lightweight lotion, or moisturizing consistency designed to deliver active ingredients deep into the skin. A quality skin serum can contribute to firmer, smoother skin texture, minimize the Appearance of pores, and boost moisture levels. Serum

formulations may include topical antibiotics, topical retinoids, and other active ingredients.[6]

Benefits of Face Serum

- Soothes irritated skin
- Absorbs quickly into the skin
- Improves the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles
- Protects the skin from free radicals and future damage[7]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Methodology

Figure 1: procedure of serum

Table 1: Formulation table

Sr no.	Ingredients	Formulation (F1)	Formulation (F2)	Formulation (F3)	Function
1	<i>Clitoria Ternatea</i> extract	5 ml	6 ml	5 ml	Antioxidant
2	Aloe vera	20 ml	20 ml	21 ml	Soothing, Moisturizing
3	Lemon oil	0.6 ml	0.5 ml	0.4 ml	Astringent
4	Sesame oil	0.6 ml	0.5 ml	0.5 ml	Moisturizing, Antioxidant
5	Glycerin	2 ml	2 ml	1 ml	Humectant
6	Tween 20	0.5 ml	0.5 ml	0.5 ml	Emulsifier
7	Ascorbic acid	0.3 gm	0.4 gm	0.5 gm	Antioxidant
8	Perfume	q.s	q.s	q.s	Fragrance
9	Water	q.s	q.s	q.s	Solvent
10	Total	30 ml	30 ml	30 ml	

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

1. Organoleptic Properties

The formulations were characterized for organoleptic properties such as colour, odour, consistency & Homogeneity. The formulations are

visually inspected for its clarity and presence of any foreign particles.

2. pH of the Serum

pH of is evaluated by pH paper. The skin has an acidic range and the pH of the skin serum should be in the range of 4.1-6.7.

3. Phase Separation

The prepared preparation was kept in a closed container at room temperature from 25 to 1000 °C protected from light. Phase separation was then checked after 24 hours. Changes in phase separation were observed.

4. Irritancy

Serum was applied to this area and the time was noted. Then, every 2-3 hours, irritation, redness and possible swelling are checked and reported. According to the result, there were no signs of irritation, erythema or swelling in the composition.[14,15,16]

5. Determination of Viscosity

Viscosity of the formulations was noted using Ostwald viscometer.

6. Anti-Microbial Assay

Antimicrobial activity of herbal face serum was done against microbial culture of Staphylococcus aureus, by using agar well diffusion method.[17,18,19]

7. Drug Excipients Compatibility Test

In this test to determine the drug excipients compatibility which includes drug as a *clitoria ternatea* and excipients used in formulation Aloe vera, glycerine, lemon oil, sesame oil, ascorbic acid, tween 20, rose water & water. Purpose of Drug-Excipients Compatibility Testing: To ensure no interaction occurs between Clitoria ternatea and the excipients that may affect various factors.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Table 2:- Result of various evaluation parameters

Sr no.	Parameters	Formulation (F1)	Formulation (F2)	Formulation (F3)
1	Organoleptic properties			
	Colour	Bluish white	Bluish white	Pale blue
	Odour	Characteristics	Characteristics	Characteristics
	Consistency	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid
	Homogeneity	Good	Good	Good
2	pH	4.68	4.5	4.89
3	Phase Separation	No	No	No
4	Irritancy	No	No	No
6	Viscosity	0.89cp	0.77cp	0.92cp

pH Test

pH test is performed by using pH paper range in between 4.1-6.7 hence the serum should be acidic range.

Figure 2: pH test of serum

Anti-microbial Assay

Anti-microbial activity was tested for the face serum and zone of inhibition is measured. The area around the antibiotic disk that has no bacterial growth is known as the zone of inhibition.

Table 4: Drug excipients compatibility test

Sr no	Excipients	Compatibility with drug- <i>clitoria ternatea</i>	Remarks
1	Aloevera	Good	Both are water soluble, soothing agent
2	Lemon oil	Moderate	Risk of oxidation need emulsifier
3	Sesame oil	Good	Natural carrier oil ; no major interaction
4	Glycerin	Very good	Hydrated stabilizer aqueous extract
5	Tween 20	Good	Solubilize lemon oil and stabilizer emulsion,
6	Ascorbic acid	Moderate	Both are antioxidant, but need pH ~4.5-5 for stability
7	Water	Good	Aqueous base compatible
8	Rose water	Good	No negative interaction; enhance fragrance

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to prepare an herbal facial serum using *Clitoria ternatea* and *Aloe barbedensis* for facial treatment. *Clitoria ternatea*,

Figure 3: Anti-Microbial assay

Table 3:-Zone of inhibition

Content	Zone of inhibition
Standard	D= 18 mm
Formulation code 1	D= 17.5 mm
Formulation code 2	D= 16 mm
Formulation code 3	D= 15 mm

Drug- Excipients Compatibility Test

Purpose of Drug-Excipients Compatibility Testing: To ensure no interaction occurs between *Clitoria ternatea* and the excipients that may affect:

- Stability
- Efficacy
- Appearance
- Safety

which is the main ingredient in the formula, has antioxidant properties for the skin. They slow down the aging of the skin. Aloe barbedensis is another important ingredient with anti-Aging and anti-inflammatory properties. Lemon oil has also been added to improve antioxidant properties. Sesame oil is used to give the serum an antimicrobial effect. Glycerin soothes the skin. Tween 20 is used as An emulsifier. A total of formulations were prepared by varying the proportion of all Ingredients. All three formulations were o/w type emulsions. All dosage forms were free of solid particles. Among the three formulations prepared, it was found to be the superior formulation based on its pH, viscosity, homogeneity, irritation and phase separation. Such a stable composition with excellent Performance can be attributed to its use.

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